

Chiral Electron-Hole Pairing as the Origin of Anomalous Quasiparticle Dispersions in Unconventional Superconductors

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The microscopic pairing mechanism in unconventional superconductors remains elusive, largely because the extreme flatness of the superconducting band often obscures key energy-momentum dispersion features observed in angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy. In this work, we re-examine high-resolution dispersion data from cuprates (Bi2212 and Bi2201) and iron-based superconductors (monolayer FeSe) to test the predictions of a newly proposed chiral electron-hole (CEH) pairing mechanism. Unlike Cooper pairs in BCS-like theories that form a single quasiparticle band with a smooth back-bending dispersion, CEH pairs exhibit a distinct two-band structure in quasiparticle dispersion with sharp cusps at the back-bending points. Our analysis identifies clear empirical signatures of these CEH-predicted features, concluding that quasiparticle dispersions in these strongly correlated materials deviate significantly from BCS-like behavior. Further comprehensive and targeted experimental strategies are proposed to definitively resolve the subtle dispersion features and rigorously test the CEH model for unconventional superconductivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Angle-resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES) [1] has emerged as an indispensable technique in the study of unconventional superconductors. Notably, it has been instrumental in determining superconducting gap symmetries, such as the discovery of the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ d-wave gap symmetry in cuprates [2]. Moreover, ARPES serves as a powerful tool for elucidating the band structures of superconducting materials, particularly by revealing the energy-momentum dispersion of the quasiparticles responsible for superconductivity.

The two primary classes of high- T_c superconductors — cuprate [3] and iron-based (FeSC) [4] materials — exhibit behaviors that diverge fundamentally from those of conventional superconductors that are well described by Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer (BCS) theory [5]. Both cuprates and FeSCs are strongly correlated electronic systems proximate to their antiferromagnetic (AFM) parent compounds, and many of their properties evade explanation within traditional BCS or BCS-like frameworks. Despite this, a 2003 ARPES study reported evidence of BCS-like quasiparticle dispersion in nearly optimally doped Bi-2223 ($T_c = 108$ K) [6]. A crucial caveat to this claim, however, is that at temperatures $T \ll T_c$, the associated band for such nearly perfect superconductors is exceedingly flat relative to the instrumental resolution of ARPES, rendering it incapable of definitively distinguishing between different types of dispersion relations.

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25 In this work, we utilize more recently published high-resolution ARPES data [7–11] to
 26 demonstrate that the quasiparticle dispersions in cuprates and FeSCs deviate significantly
 27 from BCS-like behavior. Instead, the observed dispersion features align closely with the
 28 predictions of a recently proposed pairing mechanism driven by chiral electron-hole (CEH)
 29 condensation [12]. The CEH framework intrinsically necessitates strongly correlated AFM
 30 materials for non-BCS superconductivity. Furthermore, it accounts for numerous puzzling
 31 properties observed in cuprates and FeSCs, including the pseudogap phenomenon (the ab-
 32 sence of gap closure at T_c), unexpectedly large Δ_0/T_c ratios, and a non-zero $\gamma(0)$ term and
 33 a quadratic temperature dependence in the specific heat ratio C/T as $T \rightarrow 0$ in d-wave
 34 cuprates [12].

35 In the subsequent sections, we first outline the CEH pairing mechanism and analyze
 36 its unique predicted dispersion features, specifically the emergence of two-band structures
 37 and cusps at the back-bending points. We then present and discuss detailed comparisons
 38 with recent high-resolution ARPES measurements. Ultimately, these comparisons provide
 39 compelling evidence for further systematic investigations to verify the theoretical predictions
 40 of the CEH model.

41 II. CHIRAL ELECTRON-HOLE (CEH) PAIRING

42 To introduce the CEH pairing mechanism within a mean-field framework, we begin with
 43 a four-fermion interacting Hamiltonian,

$$H = \sum_{\mathbf{k}\sigma} \xi_{\mathbf{k}} c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k}\sigma} - V \sum_{\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k}'} c_{\mathbf{k}L}^\dagger c_{-\mathbf{k}R} c_{-\mathbf{k}'R}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k}'L} \quad (1)$$

44 where $\xi_{\mathbf{k}}$ denotes the single-particle energy relative to the Fermi surface, assuming perfect
 45 particle-hole and chiral symmetries. Note that left (L) and right (R) chiralities are used
 46 here to replace the conventional up and down spin notation.

47 Traditional BCS theory postulates that a system becomes superconducting due to the
 48 condensation of electron-electron Cooper pairs $\langle c_{\mathbf{k}L} c_{-\mathbf{k}R} \rangle$. In the new CEH model, how-
 49 ever, superconductivity arises from the condensation of chiral electron-hole pairs, with the
 50 corresponding order parameter Δ defined as,

$$\Delta = V \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \langle c_{\mathbf{k}L}^\dagger c_{-\mathbf{k}R} \rangle, \quad \Delta^* = V \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \langle c_{-\mathbf{k}R}^\dagger c_{\mathbf{k}L} \rangle. \quad (2)$$

51 This leads to the following Bogoliubov-de Gennes (BdG) Hamiltonian,

$$H = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} (c_{\mathbf{k}L}^\dagger, c_{-\mathbf{k}R}^\dagger) \begin{pmatrix} \xi_{\mathbf{k}} & -\Delta^* \\ -\Delta & \xi_{\mathbf{k}} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} c_{\mathbf{k}L} \\ c_{-\mathbf{k}R} \end{pmatrix} + \frac{|\Delta|^2}{V}. \quad (3)$$

52 which can be diagonalized via the Bogoliubov transformation. The resulting eigen-energies
 53 of the Bogoliubov CEH quasiparticles are

$$E_{\mathbf{k}}^\pm = \xi_{\mathbf{k}} \pm |\Delta|, \quad (4)$$

54 which contrasts sharply with the standard BCS-like dispersion relation, $E_{\mathbf{k}}^\pm = \pm \sqrt{\xi_{\mathbf{k}}^2 + |\Delta|^2}$.
 55 This striking difference in energy-momentum dispersion constitutes the primary focus of this
 56 paper.

57 It is worth noting that both the BCS and CEH mechanisms for superconductivity bear
 58 conceptual similarities to neutrino or neutron-mirror neutron oscillations [13, 14], origi-
 59 nating from the unitary mixing between misaligned interaction and energy eigenstates. A
 60 particularly intriguing reciprocal relationship exists between the two models: the energy
 61 eigenstates of Cooper pairs are a superposition of two CEH-pair-like particles (i.e., mixing
 62 of chirally opposite electrons and holes), whereas the energy eigenstates of CEH pairs are a
 63 superposition or mixing of two Cooper-pair-like electrons or holes.

64 A fundamental distinction between the two models is that BCS quasiparticles are char-
 65 acterized by a single energy branch, $\sqrt{\xi_{\mathbf{k}}^2 + |\Delta|^2}$, whereas CEH quasiparticles possess two
 66 distinct energy branches, $|\Delta| \pm |\xi_{\mathbf{k}}|$, resulting in a two-band structure and cusps at the
 67 back-bending points. In addition, the Bogoliubov mixing angle in BCS theory, defined as
 68 $\theta_{\mathbf{k}}^{\text{BCS}} = \arctan |v_{\mathbf{k}}/u_{\mathbf{k}}|$, varies greatly between 0 and $\pi/2$ satisfying $\tan(2\theta_{\mathbf{k}}) = -|\Delta|/\xi_{\mathbf{k}}$.
 69 In contrast, the CEH mixing angle, $\theta_{\mathbf{k}}^{\text{CEH}}$, remains constant at $\pi/4$ as $|u| = |v| = 1/\sqrt{2}$
 70 assuming perfect chiral symmetry with $\xi_{\mathbf{k}L} = \xi_{\mathbf{k}R}$.

71 Depending on the orbital pairing symmetry, the CEH mechanism can yield an angular-
 72 dependent superconducting energy gap, $\Delta_{\mathbf{k}} \equiv |\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}| = \Delta\gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$. For the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ d-wave gap
 73 symmetry typical of cuprate superconductors, the symmetry factor $\gamma_{\mathbf{k}} = |\cos k_x a - \cos k_y b|/2$
 74 can be approximated as $\cos(2\varphi)$. This substitution leads to the following d-wave CEH gap
 75 equation [12],

$$\Delta(T) = \frac{8\lambda T}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi/4} d\varphi \tanh^{-1} \left(\tanh\left(\frac{\Delta(T) \cos(2\varphi)}{2T}\right) \tanh\left(\frac{\omega^*}{2T}\right) \right) \quad (5)$$

76 where the single-particle energy is integrated over the flat band (defined by $\pm\omega^*$ around
 77 the fermi surface), and $\lambda = V\rho_F$ represents the dimensionless coupling constant. Strikingly,
 78 this d-wave gap equation requires $\lambda > \pi/2$ (or $\lambda > 1$ for s-wave), indicating that the CEH
 79 mechanism is intrinsically suited for strongly correlated electron systems [12].

80 In the presence of chiral asymmetry, the modified dispersion and the Bogoliubov mixing
 81 angle can be expressed as,

$$E_{\mathbf{k}}^{\pm} = \frac{\xi_{\mathbf{k}L} + \xi_{\mathbf{k}R}}{2} \pm \sqrt{\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}^2 + \left(\frac{\xi_{\mathbf{k}L} - \xi_{\mathbf{k}R}}{2}\right)^2}, \quad (6)$$

$$\tan \theta_{\mathbf{k}}^{\text{CEH}} = \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\xi_{\mathbf{k}L} - \xi_{\mathbf{k}R}}{\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}}\right)^2} - \frac{\xi_{\mathbf{k}L} - \xi_{\mathbf{k}R}}{\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}}. \quad (7)$$

82 It is important to emphasize that the CEH pairing mechanism favors antiferromagnetism,
 83 and strong electronic correlations inherently lead to its non-local behavior. While it is well
 84 established that the superconducting gap decreases as temperature increases, the flat-band
 85 width, ω^* , may also exhibit temperature dependence, becoming flatter at lower temperatures
 86 as illustrated in the schematic diagram of Fig. 1. Crucially, the onset of superconductivity
 87 requires [12],

$$\omega^*(T) \leq \Delta(T), \quad (8)$$

88 meaning that the band ($\pm\omega^*$) in which the CEH quasiparticles form must be sufficiently flat
 89 so as not to exceed the superconducting gap Δ . No analogous requirement exists within BCS
 90 theory. Consequently, in the CEH framework, the critical temperature T_c is defined by the
 91 condition $\omega^*(T_c) = \Delta(T_c)$, whereas the gap-closing temperature T_0 is defined by $\Delta(T_0) = 0$.

FIG. 1. Schematic diagram illustrating the temperature dependence of the superconducting gap Δ and the flat-band width ω^* with the two-gap structure of $\Delta_1 = \Delta$ and $\Delta_2 = \Delta - \omega^*$. The critical temperature, T_c , is defined as the point where the band width equals the superconducting gap or $\Delta_2 = 0$, while T_0 denotes the gap-closing temperature ($\Delta_1 = 0$).

92

III. ENERGY-MOMENTUM DISPERSION

93 An optimal strategy for distinguishing the CEH quasiparticle dispersion from other BCS-
 94 like models involves conducting high-resolution ARPES measurements along the Brillouin
 95 zone (BZ) boundary, traversing an antinode and two adjacent Fermi surfaces in cuprates.
 96 In this momentum region, the unique spectral features predicted by the CEH model become
 97 pronounced. Specifically, because the two Fermi surfaces are in close proximity, the d-wave
 98 superconducting gap is near its maximum and approximately constant, allowing the single-
 99 particle dispersion to be well modeled by a parabola. Consequently, the observation of cusps
 100 at the back-bending points, alongside a distinct two-band structure, would provide definitive
 101 evidence for the CEH mechanism.

102 A schematic representation of the first Brillouin zone for the 2D CuO_2 layer is provided
 103 in the right-panel inset of Fig. 2. The thick red bar along the BZ boundary, which crosses
 104 the $(0, \pi)$ antinode, indicates the momentum trajectory along which the energy-momentum
 105 dispersion is analyzed here. This cut lies also within the AFM zone and yields a nearly
 106 constant d-wave superconducting gap, characterized by the symmetry factor $\gamma_{\mathbf{k}} = (\cos k_{\parallel} a +$
 107 $1)/2 \simeq 1$ (e.g., lattice constants $a = b = 5.4\text{\AA}$ for Bi-2212 superconductors).

108 Figure 2 illustrates the normal-state and quasiparticle energy bands relative to the Fermi
 109 level as a function of the parallel momentum along the cut and the corresponding d-wave
 110 symmetry factor $\gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$. On the left panel, the solid and dashed parabolas represent the normal-
 111 state dispersion for the electron and hole branches, respectively, residing within a relatively
 112 flat band and assuming perfect particle-hole symmetry. In the superconducting state, de-
 113 picted on the right panel, a gap opens, yielding a single quasiparticle band in each branch
 114 according to a BCS-like theory (indicated by the blue lines).

115 In contrast, the CEH mechanism generates two distinct quasiparticle bands within each

FIG. 2. Schematic comparison of the energy-momentum dispersions transitioning from the normal state (left panel) to the gapped superconducting phase (right panel) for both the CEH and BCS-like models. $\gamma_{\mathbf{k}}$ is calculated for Bi-2212. The thick red bar traversing the $(0, \pi)$ antinode in the BZ inset indicates the momentum cut corresponding to the displayed dispersions.

116 branch (denoted by solid red lines for band 1, and dashed/dotted red lines for band 2). In
 117 the superconducting phase, the primary CEH quasiparticle dispersion (band 1, representing
 118 the more energetic quasiparticles) is governed by,

$$E - E_F = \pm(|\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}| + |\xi_{\mathbf{k}}|) \quad (9)$$

119 which shows distinct, sharp cusps at the back-bending points, fundamentally differing from
 120 the smooth transitions characteristic of BCS-like dispersions. Most remarkably, unlike the
 121 BCS framework where quasiparticles share one single dispersion, CEH quasiparticles split
 122 into two distinct energy branches. The less energetic quasiparticles form a secondary band
 123 (band 2) governed by,

$$E - E_F = \pm(|\Delta_{\mathbf{k}}| - |\xi_{\mathbf{k}}|). \quad (10)$$

124 Consequently, as illustrated in Fig. 2, two corresponding energy gaps (Δ_1 and Δ_2) are
 125 associated with these distinct quasiparticle bands.

126 This two-gap feature, inherent to the CEH model and first observed in La-Bi2201 in
 127 2008 [15], naturally accounts for the pseudogap phenomenon, particularly given that $\Delta_1 =$
 128 Δ does not vanish above T_c . As such, macroscopic superconductivity emerges only when
 129 $\Delta_2 = \Delta - \omega^* > 0$, a criterion identical to the condition established in Eq. 8. It also
 130 clarifies why relatively flat bands (characterized by smaller ω^*) are a necessary precondition
 131 for CEH-driven superconductivity.

132 While the primary band (band 1) has been observed in many prior studies, explicit evi-
 133 dence of cusps at the back-bending points has remained elusive. This is largely attributable
 134 to limitations in ARPES resolution relative to the extreme flatness of these bands. Empiri-
 135 cal evidence for band 2 (the dashed and dotted red lines in Fig. 2) is even more scarce
 136 within the existing literature. In the following analysis, we present renewed evidence for
 137 both features utilizing recently published, high-resolution ARPES data.

FIG. 3. Quasiparticle dispersion at $T = 63$ K (just below $T_c = 66$ K) for the Bi-2212 sample OD66, utilizing data from Ref. [7]. Left: The CEH dispersion (solid red curve) yields an excellent fit to the experimental data; the corresponding BCS-like dispersion (dashed blue curve) is shown for comparison. Right: The best BCS-like fit (solid blue curve) fails to reproduce the observed cusps at the back-bending points.

FIG. 4. Quasiparticle dispersions at other temperatures for the Bi-2212 sample OD66, with data from Ref. [7]. The CEH dispersions (solid red curves) fit the data well, particularly in reproducing the back-bending cusps, with the notable exception of the 10 K measurement. BCS-like dispersions (dashed blue curves), calculated using the fitted normal-state dispersion, are provided for comparison.

138 Compelling evidence for the presence of cusps in band 1 is presented in Fig. 3, which
 139 displays the dispersion measured near T_c for the Bi-2212 sample OD66 [7]. This data is fitted
 140 under the assumption of a simple parabolic normal-state dispersion, implying robust chiral
 141 and particle-hole symmetries. The CEH dispersion (solid red curve, left panel) demonstrates
 142 excellent agreement with the experimental data. Conversely, the best BCS-like fit (solid blue
 143 curve, right panel) fails to reproduce the cusps at the back-bending points and it artificially
 144 requires a significantly steeper normal-state dispersion, comparable to the measurements
 145 taken at $T = 145$ K, which is at odds with the evidence discussed below.

146 Dispersions and corresponding fits at various other temperatures for the same OD66
 147 sample are detailed in Fig. 4. Because the superconducting gap is nearly constant in this
 148 momentum region, the extended “wings” beyond the back-bending points predominantly
 149 dictate the shape of the underlying single-particle (hole) parabolic dispersion that should
 150 agree with its electron counterpart determined by the quasiparticle dispersion in between
 151 the back-bending points assuming particle-hole symmetry. Notably, the band flattens at
 152 lower temperatures, indicative of an increasing effective mass as the system cools.

153 The measurement at $T = 63$ K provides the clearest resolution of the cusp feature by
 154 striking an optimal balance between minimized experimental uncertainty and a band that
 155 is not yet excessively flat compared to lower-temperature data (as shown in Fig. S1). Con-
 156 sequently, fits at other temperatures are comparatively less definitive. Specifically, the fit
 157 at $T = 10$ K is limited by the extreme flatness of the band at such a low temperature. The
 158 extracted normal-state dispersions at these temperatures with fitting parameters summa-
 159 rized in Table I are plotted in Fig. S2, consistently demonstrating the progressive flattening
 160 of the band as temperature decreases. This temperature-dependent flattening is indepen-
 161 dently corroborated by the findings in Figs. 3i–j and S13a–b of Ref. [7], which show that
 162 the normal-state dispersion at 86 K (where the gap is nearly closed) is substantially flatter
 163 than the one at 145 K.

164 Further evidence of cusps in band 1 is provided in Fig. 5 with fitting parameters sum-
 165 marized in Table II, displaying data for the Bi-2212 sample OD49 [7]. Here, the dispersions
 166 exhibit even more pronounced cusps due to the reduced flatness of the superconducting
 167 band. However, this sample also presents stronger chiral and particle-hole asymmetries.
 168 To better fit the quasiparticle dispersion, an averaged experimental normal-state dispersion
 169 (black stars in the right panel of Fig. 5), measured at higher temperatures, is scaled down,
 170 using distinct scaling factors for the electron and hole branches to account for the band flat-
 171 ness at lower temperatures. Such scaling is demonstrated for the 45-K fit on the right panel.
 172 The discrepancies observed at the right back-bending points likely originate from misaligned
 173 single-particle dispersions near the Fermi level (unaccounted in the fitting), which is also
 174 visible, albeit to a much lesser extent, in the OD66 data (Fig. S1).

175 Arguably the most comprehensive evidence capturing the features of both CEH bands
 176 is found in the ARPES data (Fig. 6) for superconducting monolayer FeSe films grown on
 177 SrTiO₃ [8]. These spectra were acquired along a momentum cut through an electron pocket
 178 centered at the M-point, which is analogous to the antinodal cut analyzed in the cuprates.
 179 CEH band 1 traced by the solid red curve and band 2 indicated by the dashed red line in
 180 Fig. 6c, originally conflated as labels A' and B in the source reference, are both clearly
 181 resolved. Because these bands are situated deeply (~ 100 meV below the Fermi surface)
 182 and lack the extreme flatness seen in cuprates, the signature CEH features are starkly
 183 visible. Although the band closer to the Fermi surface (band A, marked by the blue line)
 184 is the one primarily responsible for superconductivity in this system, the authors of Ref.

FIG. 5. Left: Dispersion data at varied temperatures for the Bi-2212 sample OD49 from Ref. [7], overlaid with CEH fits (red curves). Select datasets are offset as labeled for clarity. Right: Average normal-state dispersion data (black stars) acquired between 65 K and 95 K (from Fig. S14b of Ref. [7]), and its scaling demonstration for a representative CEH fit at $T = 45$ K, which uses the solid and dashed red curves with band scaling factors of 0.38 and 0.23 for the electron and hole normal states, respectively.

185 [8] convincingly demonstrated that these deeper CEH bands are exclusively associated with
 186 superconducting monolayer FeSe and are entirely absent in non-superconducting multilayer
 187 samples.

188 These quasiparticle dispersion relations in FeSe are further illustrated by the waterfall
 189 plot of energy distribution curves (EDCs) in Fig. 6a [8]. In this representation, the central
 190 segment of CEH band 2 (corresponding to the dashed red lines in Figs. 2 and 6c) manifests
 191 clearly as a structural shoulder next to CEH band 1. Intriguingly, similar shoulder features
 192 have been reported in the literature for other superconductors. For instance, the data for
 193 Bi-2201 shown in Fig. S3 [9] explicitly display this shoulder feature characteristic of band
 194 2, and simultaneously exhibit indications of cusps in band 1. The shoulder feature becomes
 195 more pronounced at lower temperatures, as illustrated in similar plots in Figs. 2 and 4 of
 196 Ref. [9], Fig. 1 of Ref. [10], and Fig. 4 of Ref. [11].

197 Despite these observations, the extended “wings” of band 2 (represented by the dotted
 198 red lines in Fig. 2) seem to be much less discernible in published data. A weak spectral
 199 feature (labeled as band C in Fig. 6b) may offer tentative evidence of their existence. More
 200 inspiringly, the temperature-dependent ARPES spectra and EDC plots from Ref. [7] (Figs.
 201 3e-h and S13c-f therein) reveal ridges crossing the Fermi surfaces that start to develop near
 202 or above T_c . These ridges could plausibly represent the emerging wings of band 2. Future
 203 investigations, particularly those leveraging advanced ARPES image-processing techniques,
 204 are essential to definitively isolate and clarify this subtle spectral feature.

FIG. 6. Quasiparticle band dispersions intersecting an electron pocket centered at the M-point for monolayer FeSe on SrTiO₃ [8]. (a) EDCs presented as a waterfall plot. (b) Second-derivative intensity plot at 16 K, with bands labeled corresponding to (a). (c,d) Intensity plots at different temperatures; the solid red curve traces CEH band 1, while the dashed red line indicates CEH band 2. Adapted from Figs. 1 and 3 of Ref. [8].

205

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

206 We have re-examined previously published data to present compelling evidence for the
 207 unique two-band structure and cusp features in quasiparticle dispersion, as predicted by the
 208 recently proposed chiral electron-hole pairing mechanism for non-BCS superconductivity. To
 209 further validate these findings, future high-precision ARPES studies are essential, particu-
 210 larly those focused on the antinodal cut along the BZ boundary in cuprates and the M-point
 211 cut in FeSCs. Comprehensive and systematic measurements of these materials across a
 212 wider range of doping levels and temperatures are highly encouraged. Specifically, to make
 213 signatures like the back-bending cusps more pronounced, experimental efforts should target
 214 underdoped or sub-optimal superconductors near T_c , where the associated superconducting
 215 bands exhibit reduced flatness. Finally, to better visualize and extract these complex quasi-
 216 particle dispersions, analyses must move beyond the simple fitting of EDC maxima. The
 217 application of advanced techniques such as the second-derivative approach, the curvature
 218 method [16], and possibly machine learning algorithms and emerging AI technology, will be
 219 critical for definitively resolving these subtle spectral features in future research.

220

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225

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

226 This appendix provides additional experimental dispersion data and normal-state deriva-
 227 tions used to support the fits in the main text.

FIG. S1. Experimental dispersions at varied temperatures for the Bi-2212 sample OD66 [7], obtained by fitting the maxima of Fermi-function-divided EDCs, as provided by the original authors. Data for 68 K and 73 K are taken from Fig. S16a,d of Ref. [7], while the remaining data are sourced from Figs. 3k and S15 of the same reference. Select dispersion curves are vertically offset by a few meV for clarity, as labeled. The red curves in the right panel are generated by applying the CEH fitting results from the lower branch to the upper branch, with slight shifts incorporated to account for particle-hole asymmetry.

TABLE I. CEH fitting parameters for Figs. 3-4.

T [K]	normal-state parabola [meV]	Δ [meV]
10	$371.27(k_{\parallel} + 0.03609)(k_{\parallel} - 0.04341)$	18.57
58	$618.15(k_{\parallel} + 0.03198)(k_{\parallel} - 0.03915)$	15.47
63	$771.14(k_{\parallel} + 0.03720)(k_{\parallel} - 0.04039)$	12.04
68	$916.06(k_{\parallel} + 0.03667)(k_{\parallel} - 0.04116)$	10.29
73	$1029.61(k_{\parallel} + 0.03108)(k_{\parallel} - 0.04188)$	8.40

FIG. S2. Normal-state dispersion data at $T = 145$ K from Ref. [7] and CEH-fitted normal-state dispersion curves at varied temperatures derived from the CEH fits presented in Figs. 3–4.

FIG. S3. Quasiparticle band dispersions along the antinodal cut at 10 K for Bi-2201 [9]. Left: EDC waterfall plot. Right: Energy-momentum dispersion curves. Green circles denote the shoulder feature corresponding to CEH band 2, while blue circles indicate CEH band 1 and its cusp feature. Adapted from Fig. 2 of [9].

TABLE II. CEH fitting parameters for Fig. 5.

T [K]	scaling factor for electron branch	scaling factor for hole branch	Δ [meV]
26	0.24	0.10	11.5
35	0.26	0.12	10.3
45	0.38	0.23	7.7
55	0.48	0.36	5.5

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